

Transfer of Civil Liability in Fire Insurance with Emphasis on Insurance Contractual Clauses

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Author: Behrad Ehsani¹

Supervisor: Dr. Mehdi Yousefi Sadeghlou²

Advisor: Dr. Hossein Sartipi

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Abstract:

In fire insurance policies, when one of the risks covered by the policy occurs and causes damage to the insured's property, the insurer is only obligated to compensate the financial losses sustained by the insured person. However, it is possible that damage may also be inflicted upon neighboring buildings or shared spaces. In such cases, according to the Iranian Civil Liability Law, the insured individual is responsible for the damage caused (whether bodily or financial) to neighbors; nevertheless, standard fire insurance policies generally do not provide coverage for this scenario. Therefore, in addition to purchasing fire insurance, the policyholder must obtain civil liability insurance arising from fire incidents. Through this type of liability insurance, bodily and financial damages caused to neighbors and third parties—subject to the conditions and clauses stipulated within the insurance contract—will be compensated by the insurer (up to the coverage limit stated in the policy). Thus, by entering into an insurance contract, the responsibility for such compensation can be transferred to the insurer. However, the contractual clauses of the insurance policy play a crucial role as complementary elements in determining the effects of insurance contracts. Accordingly, this study aims to examine the nature of both fire insurance and civil liability insurance, to identify the contractual clauses that enable the transfer of civil liability to the insurer, and to analyze the obstacles to such transfer based on legal materials and sources. The findings indicate that the transfer of civil liability to the insurer is based on the insurance contract, and the obligations of the parties are strictly limited to the terms and clauses set forth in the contract. Therefore, the insurer's liability towards the policyholder or, consequently, third parties is limited to the insured amount specified in the policy. This research is a descriptive-analytical study, examining fire insurance and civil liability arising from fire, with data collected primarily through library research methods.

Keywords:

Insurance Contract, Civil Liability, Fire Insurance, Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire, Contractual Clauses in Insurance

1. Introduction

In the Iranian legal system, every individual is held responsible for bodily or financial harm caused to others as a result of carelessness or negligence, and is required to compensate for such damages. In these circumstances, civil liability insurance plays a significant role in transferring the financial burden of this responsibility. This type of

insurance is offered in various forms and, in cases such as fire, may cover damages caused to third parties or the property of neighbors—provided the insured has obtained a separate civil liability insurance policy. Nonetheless, the contractual clauses of the insurance policy are of particular importance, and neglecting these clauses by the policyholders may result in the insurer's obligations being rendered void. From a legal perspective, a

¹ Legal Consultant | LL.M. in Private Law | MBA | Certified Arbitrator | Independent Researcher ;ehsani@disroot.org
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2243-3814> ; (Bar Association Profile)<https://icbars.org/Lawyer/1987895431>

² m_yousefi_2005@pnu.ac.ir

precise examination of the parties' obligations and the legal guarantees for the enforcement of those obligations is essential to determine the scope of each party's legal responsibility. The commercial insurance industry plays a fundamental role in economic development and in protecting society against losses resulting from incidents, especially fires. Despite the high frequency of fire-related incidents and the severe financial and personal damages they cause in Iran, fire insurance has not yet gained the recognition it deserves among the general population. Under current conditions, obtaining fire insurance is highly necessary and cost-effective for residents, particularly in metropolitan areas, and can provide assurance for the future livelihoods of individuals. However, achieving this goal depends on policyholders' awareness of the contractual clauses and their compliance with them. Therefore, examining the transfer of civil liability in fire insurance policies and understanding the contractual clauses of insurance contracts holds particular importance and necessity, as it leads to greater clarity regarding the parties' obligations. To date, there has been no independent research specifically addressing civil liability in fire insurance and the obligations of the parties involved. However, some related studies have indirectly touched upon the subject; for example, Naeiminejad (2012) explored the civil liability of physicians and the need for legislative reforms in liability law; Moezi (2007) discussed the importance of contractual clauses in third-party insurance and the role of compensation tools; and Shahidi-Zandi (2014) addressed the nature and legal effects of life insurance contracts and the need for uniform and transparent legislation. While these studies do not directly examine the present research topic, they do address issues related to obligations and liabilities arising from insurance contracts, thereby confirming the existing research gap concerning fire insurance and the obligations of contracting parties. The primary aim of this research is to examine and clarify the transfer of civil

liability in fire insurance policies, with particular emphasis on the contractual clauses. Civil liability insurance arising from fire only covers losses suffered by third parties if the insured's responsibility is established and in accordance with the terms of the contract. Secondary objectives of this research include the examination and explanation of the nature and foundations of civil liability, analysis of fire insurance and the resulting civil liability, and evaluation of contractual clauses in civil liability insurance policies. Clarifying these issues contributes to legal order and to a more precise determination of the parties' obligations and responsibilities under the insurance contract. The main hypothesis asserts that the transfer of civil liability to the insurer is based on the insurance contract. The subsidiary hypotheses further emphasize that:

- The transfer of liability does not completely absolve the insured from responsibility, and the insured remains liable for the amount of damages;
- The transfer of liability is subject to specific conditions;
- The insurer's liability is limited to the coverage limit specified in the policy.

This study employs a descriptive-analytical approach, utilizing library and documentary research methods. Data and information required for the analysis have been collected from reputable scientific sources, including books, articles, legal journals, and online databases.

2. Theoretical Foundations and Fundamental Concepts

2.1 The Basis of Civil Liability

Civil liability, also referred to as "ghahri responsibility" (non-contractual liability), means the legal obligation of an individual to compensate for loss or damage caused to another as a result of an act attributable to him (Rezaei, 2018). This liability is

connected to ethical and religious rules, and its main purpose is to compensate the loss incurred by the injured party and to protect individuals' private rights. The sources of this liability are cited in Articles 308 to 337 of the Civil Code, the Law of Civil Liability, and the Law of Compulsory Insurance for Motor Vehicle Owners. Civil liability must be distinguished from contractual liability. Contractual liability arises from the breach of obligations stipulated in the contract between the parties, and its subject is always the payment of damages due to breach of contract (Esfandiari, 2016; Habibzadeh, 2017). In this type of liability, a mere breach of contract constitutes a violation, and the obligor will only be exempt in case of proven force majeure. However, in civil (non-contractual) liability, proof of the tortfeasor's fault and its relation to the damage is required, and there is usually no contractual relationship between the parties (Barikloo, 2013, p. 22; Beigdeli, 2014). Moral responsibility means the accountability of a person with respect to his moral duties, so that if he fulfills his duties, he is worthy of praise, and otherwise, he deserves blame. The realization of moral responsibility requires the individual's awareness, will, and capacity regarding his action. The fundamental difference with civil liability is that moral responsibility pertains to the individual's relationship with God or personal conscience, and a mere inappropriate act (even without causing loss to others) is grounds for responsibility; whereas civil liability is concerned with compensation for loss incurred by another, and its sanction is compensation for the injured party (Shokri, 2011). Criminal liability means the individual's accountability before the law for committing a criminal act and requires intent or will in committing the offense and a causal relationship between the act and the result. The main purpose of criminal liability is to punish the offender for the protection of society, maintaining order, and reforming the offender, while civil liability is solely aimed at compensating the loss of the injured

person (Hozouri, 2021). In criminal liability, the damage is to society and the occurrence of the offense requires criminal intent or fault, whereas in civil liability, proof of bad faith is not required, and mere carelessness, recklessness, or non-observance of regulations is sufficient. The investigation of criminal offenses is mostly conducted through the prosecutor's office and law enforcement, while civil claims are addressed in civil courts. Criminal justice also requires consideration of the personality and individual circumstances of the offender in determining the punishment, while in civil liability, this is not necessary (Erfanipour, 2013). In Iranian law, which is based on Islamic jurisprudence and relevant laws (such as the Civil Code and the Islamic Penal Code), mere proof of loss and the existence of a causal relationship between the act or omission and the loss is sufficient for establishing civil liability and the obligation to compensate; there is no need to prove fault (Articles 328 and 331 of the Civil Code). In contrast, the Law of Civil Liability enacted in 1960 regards liability as being based on proof of the tortfeasor's fault and does not consider a mere causal relationship sufficient. Thus, there is a fundamental difference between the basis of civil liability in the Civil Code and in the Law of Civil Liability. However, considering the position of Islamic jurisprudence in Iranian law, the prevailing rule is liability based on the existence of a causal relationship and not solely on fault (Babaei, 2018, p. 105). To justify the appropriate basis for the liability of the injurer, jurists have expressed various theories, the most important of which are briefly mentioned below:

2.1.1 Fault Theory

The fault theory is one of the oldest foundations of civil liability. According to this theory, the injured party must prove the fault of the injurer in order to receive compensation. This theory is based on the presumption of innocence, and the burden of proving fault lies with the injured party. The

Civil Code, in Articles 951 and 952, defines excess and negligence and states the liability resulting from the failure to exercise usual caution or exceeding customary limits. Article 1 of the Law of Civil Liability also extends liability to life, health, reputation, and freedom. However, proving fault is difficult for the injured party, and in cases such as legally incompetent minors and the insane, there is no liability, which is a major criticism of this theory (Dashti Zangir, 2019).

2.1.2 Risk Theory (Strict Liability)

The risk theory, introduced by Saleilles and Josserand, states that for civil liability to be realized, proof of fault is not necessary; the mere occurrence of a harmful act is sufficient for the injurer to be liable for compensation. In this theory, liability lies with the person who benefits from an activity or ownership and creates risk; thus, the principle is the liability of the injurer, and he must prove otherwise. This theory has developed through approaches such as the absolute risk theory or risk arising from material benefit, and its impact is evident in the French workplace accident laws (1898), Iran's Social Security Law (1975), and the decision of the French Supreme Court (1930). Additionally, this view corresponds with the principle of "man lahu al-ghunm fa'alayhi al-ghurm" (whoever benefits bears the loss) in Islamic jurisprudence (Irani, 2019; Dehghani Tafti, 2020).

2.1.3 Right Guarantee Theory

According to the right guarantee theory proposed by Boris Stark, every individual in society has the right to live in safety and health, and any harm to these rights entails the civil liability of the violator (Parvizianjali, 2018). This theory emphasizes the conflict between the "right to security" and the "right to activity"; where the right to security prevails (such as the right to life and property), any harm must be compensated. However, in cases of purely economic or moral damages, compensation

is contingent upon proving the fault of the injurer (Salehi Zahabi, 2002). The strength of this theory is its protection of the rights of victims, while its weakness is that it deprives the injurer of the possibility of defense.

2.2 Elements of Civil Liability

For civil liability to be established, the existence of three essential elements is necessary:

A harmful act is an act performed without legal authorization and attributable to the injurer; if the act is performed with legal authorization, the person is not responsible for the resulting damage (Behroozizadeh, 2017). The occurrence of actual (real), direct, and uncompensated damage is a primary condition for liability, and only losses arising from legal rights are claimable (Rahimi & Hajiban, 2014). Finally, there must be a recognized and direct causal relationship between the harmful act and the resulting damage for civil liability to be realized (causal relationship).

2.3 The Insurance Contract and Its Characteristics

Today, the insurance industry, as one of the main tools for risk coverage and distribution in economic systems, plays a significant role in improving the economic structure, increasing investment, enhancing social welfare, and facilitating financial credits (Mary Kelly, 2017). Without insurance, businesses and job creation would face serious challenges. Technically, insurance is an operation in which the insurer, by gathering policyholders and receiving premiums, undertakes to compensate for losses incurred in the event of a risk or incident (Maurice Picard and André Besson, Hamard, Fourastier – quoted in Jahanshahi, 2013; Farjadi, 1997, pp. 21-24). In Iran, Article 1 of the Insurance Law of 1937 defines insurance as a contract whereby the insurer, in return for receiving a premium, undertakes to compensate for the loss or pay a specific sum to the policyholder in the

event of an incident (Arzhang et al., 2014). Although this definition is not comprehensive, it explains the essential principles of insurance, and a more technical definition requires attention to risk management and the rules of statistics and probabilities (Farjadi, 1997, p. 24; Moein, 2000, p. 633; Vojdani, 1992; Ghanbari, 2015). In commercial insurance, four main elements exist:

- The insurer is a legal entity (a public joint-stock company, private or state-owned) which, in exchange for receiving the premium, is obliged to implement the contract's terms and compensate the policyholder or beneficiary.
- The policyholder (Policy-Holder) is a natural or legal person who signs the insurance application and is responsible for paying the premium. He or she may be a principal or an agent, attorney, guarantor, etc.
- The insured, in personal insurance, is the individual whose life or death is the subject of insurance and whose written consent is necessary for the contract's validity; in non-personal insurance, the insured is the property or interest being insured.
- The beneficiary is a natural or legal person who benefits from the insurance and may be designated by the policyholder at the time of contracting or during the contract; in the absence of designation, the legal heirs are considered beneficiaries (Farjadi, 1997, p. 25).

Familiarity with specialized insurance terminology is essential for understanding obligations and achieving success in this field.

- The insurance proposal (Application) is an official form completed by the policyholder, providing the insurer with the necessary information about the policyholder, the insured subject, and possible risks.
- The insurance contract (Policy) is a document issued by the insurer and is the

source of the parties' obligations and requirements.

- The endorsement (Endorsement) is an official document that adds changes or new conditions to the insurance contract and is an integral part of it (Farjadi, 1997, p. 29).
- The sum insured is the maximum financial obligation of the insurer in each incident or insurance period.
- Loss is the financial harm to the insured subject, which may be total or partial, direct or indirect (Farjadi, 1997, p. 30).
- Indemnity is the agreed sum paid to the victim or his/her survivors in the event of an incident, and its amount may be determined by agreement or by law (Farjadi, 1997, p. 30).
- In insurance, loss means the occurrence of a risk that the insurer is obliged to compensate; risk refers to a probable incident that causes harm to the policyholder (Farjadi, 1997, p. 30).

According to Article 182 of the Civil Code and Article 1 of the Insurance Law, the insurance contract is a contract that has all the pillars of a contract (declaration of contract, parties, subject, and consideration) (Jamali Zadeh, 2008). The purpose of this contract is to provide the policyholder with assurance that possible losses will be compensated by the insurer, and the transfer of responsibility is realized only by observing the contractual clauses of insurance. The insurance contract is a binding contract; that is, the parties cannot unilaterally terminate it, except in cases stipulated by law or in the private conditions of the policy (Al-Sheikh, 2002, pp. 105-138; Zeinali, 2020, p. 17). The policyholder's obligations are certain, and payment of the premium is not contingent upon the occurrence of an incident, but the insurer's obligation is usually suspended pending the occurrence of the insured risk; therefore, the insurance contract is conditional on one side. After the enactment of the Insurance Law in 1937, the insurance contract has its own specific name and conditions in the law and

is considered a named contract. Insurance is a commutative contract: the policyholder undertakes to pay the premium, and in return, the insurer undertakes to compensate the loss or pay a certain amount. Although the insurance contract can be concluded verbally and the principle of validity of transactions applies, it is preferable for it to be in writing for proof and transparency (Mazdarani, 2017; Mahdavi, 2019, p. 145). The insurance contract is an adhesion contract: the insurer sets the terms, and the policyholder can only accept or reject them; therefore, insurance is considered an adhesion contract (Kharoushi, 2011; Zeinali, 2020, p. 18). The effects of the insurance contract and the obligations of the parties continue throughout the contract period; thus, the insurance contract is a continuous contract. The performance of the insurer's obligation depends on the occurrence of an incident, and the realization of the loss is based on probability and chance; therefore, the insurance contract is aleatory.

2.4 Types of Insurance Policies

In one classification, insurance policies are divided into marine and non-marine (social and commercial) categories. Commercial insurance also includes property insurance (such as fire insurance, vehicle body insurance) and civil liability insurance. Civil liability insurance is further divided into branches such as employer's liability, professional liability, manufacturers' liability, public liability, and liability arising from contracts (Naseri, 2007).

- **Employer's liability insurance towards employees:** According to the law, employers are obligated to observe safety and protect their employees, and in the event of an accident involving workers, the insurer compensates for bodily and financial damages (such as death, disability, and medical expenses). This insurance policy covers employers of service, manufacturing, industrial units, and contractors of construction projects.

- **Professional liability insurance:** Professional liability insurance is provided for those who, due to error, negligence, or omission in their profession, cause damage to others. This insurance policy covers professions such as managers, doctors, engineers, managers of public places, trainers, and other responsible individuals against damages inflicted on third parties or clients.

- **Manufacturers' liability insurance:** This insurance policy holds manufacturers responsible for bodily or financial damages caused to consumers and third parties due to defects and faults in products, and the insurer is responsible for compensating for the respective damages.

- **Public liability insurance:** This insurance assists in regulating social relations, raising awareness of rights and responsibilities, and providing professional security. Liabilities such as the liability of municipalities towards citizens, liability arising from fire incidents with respect to neighbors, liability of contractors, exhibition managers, and so on, fall under this category (Montazeri, 2019).

2.5 Fire Insurance

Fire has long been one of the most significant risks constantly threatening human life and property. Fire insurance, as one of the oldest and principal types of insurance, plays a considerable role in providing economic security and psychological peace for individuals and society, and its development is more complete and advanced compared to many other branches of insurance. Even in other insurance branches, coverage for damages caused by fire is one of the insurer's main obligations (for example, automobile insurance, cargo insurance, marine insurance, life, and accident insurance). The subject of fire insurance is the compensation for financial losses sustained by the insured property (both movable and immovable) as a result of fire. According to the general terms of fire insurance policies, "fire" refers to

severe or rapid burning accompanied by flames. Therefore, damages caused by slow or controlled burning (such as by heaters or stoves) are not covered by this insurance. Fire insurance, in addition to compensating for direct damages caused by fire, lightning, and explosion, also compensates for damages and costs resulting from necessary actions to prevent the spread of fire or the emergency transfer of property for its rescue. However, bodily injuries and personal compensation are usually not covered by this insurance policy unless explicitly mentioned in the contract. In addition to the main risks (fire, explosion, lightning), subsidiary and additional risks such as earthquake, airplane crash, bursting of water pipes, theft, etc., can also be covered in fire insurance policies, each with its own terms and premium rates. Non-material damages such as deprivation of use of the damaged property, factory shutdown, or loss of income are covered only if specifically stated in the insurance policy and special conditions are included. Also, if a fire causes damage to third parties (for example, the owner's liability towards tenants or neighbors), such liabilities can be covered by liability insurance. The insured property in fire insurance can include household furniture (all items and equipment used by family members in the residence), machinery and industrial or commercial equipment (whether installed or not), materials and products (such as raw materials, products under construction or finished, and packaging materials), and the property of other persons (provided that it is included in the insured capital and located at the insured premises). According to Article 14 of the Law on Ownership of Apartments, insuring the entire building against fire is mandatory, and building managers must insure it as a single unit. Furthermore, the insured location plays an important role in determining the premium rate and the insurer's obligations, and transferring insured property to another location without coordination results in loss of insurance coverage. According to the general principles of property insurance,

principles such as the principle of indemnity, principle of subrogation, principle of good faith, insurable interest principle, the rule of proportional capital (loss), and the principle of contribution also apply to fire insurance (Yamini, 2003). Finally, some items (such as cash, securities, jewelry, etc.) are by default not covered by fire insurance unless explicitly stated in the contract.

2.5.1 Types of Risks Covered in Fire Insurance

The risks covered by fire insurance are divided into two main and subsidiary groups. The first group includes the principal risks, namely fire, explosion, and lightning, which the policyholder must simultaneously cover in the policy (Yamini, 2003, p. 23). Subsidiary risks, such as earthquake, flood, storm, bursting of water pipes, airplane crash, strike and riot, cleanup costs, glass breakage, etc., can be separately added to the policy with their specific rates, and are not insurable without coverage of the principal risks.

a) Fire: Fire means the combination of a combustible material with oxygen, resulting in flame and heat. The Iranian Insurance Law has not defined "fire," but relies on its conventional meaning (Yamini, 2003, p. 23).

b) Explosion: In fire insurance, explosion refers to the sudden release of energy resulting from the expansion of gas or steam, causing damage to property. Some explosions, such as nuclear explosions, are not covered.

c) Lightning: Lightning includes the discharge of electrical charge and the direct damage resulting from it. Some indirect damages, such as the malfunction of devices due to electrical energy from lightning, are not covered.

d) Earthquake and Volcano: In the event of an earthquake or volcano, direct damage to buildings and their contents can be insured.

e) Flood and Overflow: Flood means the sudden flow of water outside its natural course, and, if insured, the damages incurred are compensated.

f) Storm and Tornado: If this coverage is added, damages caused by strong winds are also insured.

g) Bursting of Water Pipes and Damage from Snow and Rain: These damages, with the addition of specific conditions to the policy, can be covered.

h) Airplane and Helicopter Crash: Damages caused by the crash or objects dropped from these vehicles are compensated up to the insured amount.

i) Strike, Riot, Civil Commotion, Uprising: Coverage for damages resulting from these events depends on the payment of additional premium and compliance with specific conditions. Damages resulting from war, rebellion, revolution, confiscation, and expropriation are generally not covered.

j) Cleanup Costs: If included in the policy, up to 20% of the insured value can be compensated for cleanup costs after the incident.

k) Impact by Foreign Object: If the insured location is exposed to risks such as proximity to a road or hill, additional coverage is provided.

l) Spontaneous Combustion: Some materials have the property of spontaneous combustion and are covered under special conditions (Yamini, 2003, p. 46).

m) Glass Breakage: Installed glass in the building, if broken due to an accident, is insured under specific conditions.

n) Burglary with Forced Entry: Burglaries involving illegal entry (such as breaking a door or window), upon the policyholder's

request and specific conditions in the policy, are covered.

o) Loss of Profit Due to Fire: By agreement, the insurer may also compensate for damages due to business interruption or loss of profit (Naseri, 2007; Yamini, 2003, p. 52). This coverage is mainly provided in cargo insurance or by special agreement.

p) Industrial Pressure Vessels: Damages resulting from the explosion of industrial pressure vessels are only compensated by adding specific coverage.

In all these cases, the specific terms and exclusions for each insurance policy must be stated precisely, and sometimes certain damages or events (such as war and widespread unrest) are entirely excluded from insurance coverage.

2.6 Contractual Clauses in Fire Insurance

In the fire insurance contract, in addition to the main obligations established by law for the insurer and the policyholder, the parties can also specify subsidiary obligations by including contractual clauses in the agreement (Jamali Zadeh, 2008). Contractual clauses are agreements arranged alongside the principal contract and can create additional duties or rights for one or both parties (Khajeh Torab, 2018). These clauses usually pertain to operational details such as the manner of premium payment, conditions for termination of the contract, or procedures for reporting and managing claims. The section of contractual clauses is usually standardized and, in particular, defines the obligations of the policyholder in the event of an incident as well as the rights of the insurance company in cases where the risk, controllable by the policyholder, is aggravated (Mahdavi, 2019, p. 172). Generally, just as in other contracts (such as the contract of sale), besides the main obligations, the parties may, by mutual agreement, add other obligations, the same applies to fire insurance. The inclusion of

these clauses results in greater transparency and prevents disputes. The conditions in the fire insurance policy consist of three parts:

2.6.1 General Conditions of Fire Insurance

General conditions in fire insurance policies are usually prepared in printed and standardized form and are the same for all policyholders throughout the country. These clauses set forth the fundamental principles of the contract, the obligations and duties of the insurer and the policyholder before and after an incident, the conditions for termination and annulment, transfer of the policy, the conditions of insured risks and exclusions, the method of reporting and assessing claims, as well as the process for determining and paying compensation (Yamini, 2003, p. 53). In this section, the key concepts and necessary definitions for understanding the other provisions of the contract are also provided, and a framework is considered for calculating the premium and managing potential claims arising from the contract. In fact, the general conditions, based on the country's general laws and insurance regulations, ensure the integrity and legal coherence of the insurance policies.

2.6.2 Specific Conditions of Fire Insurance

Specific conditions define the special circumstances of each policy and are drawn up separately for each insurance contract. This section includes detailed and specific information such as: complete particulars of the insurer (name, address, registration number, capital, statutory reserves), policy number and date of issuance, period of validity, amount of insured capital or the insurer's liability limit, premium details and method of payment, amount of deductible, complete information about the insured subject, beneficiaries, rates and special conditions related to the policy, as well as the geographical area of coverage. Due to their particular nature, specific conditions take precedence over general conditions and have

priority over general matters, as they reflect the specific agreements of the parties in each contract and are different for each policyholder.

2.6.3 Exclusion Clauses in Fire Insurance

Exclusion clauses or insurance exceptions are a part of every insurance policy that specifies the risks or incidents for which the insurer bears no liability for compensation (Yamini, 2003, p. 53). Exclusions are divided into general and specific categories. General exclusions, such as damages resulting from war, riot, or earthquake, are mentioned in most insurance policies and are generally not covered unless an additional premium is paid (Article 28 of the Insurance Law of 1937). Specific exclusions are also specified separately for each branch of insurance or particular type of policy; for example, damage to precious metals or important documents is often excluded from the insurer's obligations unless otherwise stipulated (Article 20 and Article 28 of the Insurance Law of 1937; Articles 30 to 34 of Regulation No. 21 of the Supreme Council of Insurance, 1987). In fire insurance, the following are excluded from the insurer's obligations unless explicitly stated in the policy:

- Coins, money, securities, documents, precious metals and jewelry, costs of reconstructing plans and data collection (Regulation No. 21).
- Damage resulting from war, riot, strike, civil commotion, earthquake, flood, explosion of explosives, nuclear reactions, and underground fire (Article 28 of the Insurance Law; Regulation No. 21).
- Damage to electric motors and machines caused by electrical connection or similar effects, unless damage is caused to other parts of the insured property (Regulation No. 21).

- Damage to industrial pressure vessels caused by explosion; however, damage to other sections is covered (same).
- Damage occurring within the area of controlled fire (same).

In liability insurance resulting from fire, according to Article 28 of the Insurance Law and Article 2 of the General Conditions of the Civil Liability Insurance Policy for Fire, damages to the property of third parties unless expressly stated otherwise, bodily compensation for the policyholder and relatives, damages resulting from willful misconduct, fraud, or nuclear explosion and war are also outside the insurer's obligations.

2.6.4 Deductible Clause in Fire Insurance

A deductible clause is a provision by which, in the event of a loss, part of the loss is borne by the policyholder and the insurer has no obligation for that portion (Yamini, 2003). This share may be a fixed amount, a percentage of the insured sum, or a percentage of the amount of loss, as specified in the policy. The determination of a deductible serves several purposes: firstly, by setting a deductible, the premium can be adjusted and reduced; secondly, the existence of a deductible increases the care and caution of the policyholder regarding the insured property; thirdly, because policyholders pay part of the loss, they often refrain from claiming for minor damages, which brings financial benefits for insurers (same). In fire insurance, the main risks are usually covered without a deductible, but for subsidiary risks and in civil liability insurance arising from fire, the deductible is usually determined by agreement of the parties (same).

2.7 Civil Liability Insurance

In society, every individual, by virtue of their social role, is responsible towards third parties and may inadvertently cause harm to the life or property of others. According to the law, the injuring party, upon fulfillment

of the relevant conditions, is obliged to compensate for the damage caused, and this obligation can be covered by civil liability insurance (Ghaffari, 2017). Types of civil liability insurance are defined based on the type of activity and individuals' roles; for example: insurance for managers and kindergarten teachers covers only bodily injuries to children within the kindergarten premises and does not include commuting routes or property damage; professional liability insurance for physicians compensates for losses caused by medical error and negligence to patients; and insurance for construction engineers covers bodily and financial damages to owners, workers, and third parties in construction projects. Professional liability insurance for hotel managers covers bodily and financial damages to guests in the accommodation and public areas of the hotel. Similarly, insurance for pool managers and parking lot operators covers damages to visitors and users. What matters in civil liability insurance is the compensation of third-party damages so that the insured can continue their activities with peace of mind. According to the Insurance Law of the People's Republic of China, liability insurance is defined as accepting the policyholder's responsibility for damages caused to third parties, and in the event of an incident, the insurer undertakes to pay compensation and medical expenses (Rui-xia, 2011). With the expansion of social activities, purchasing civil liability insurance has become a necessity for individuals and organizations (Ghaffari, 2017).

2.7.1 Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire

Civil liability insurance arising from fire is a subset of public liability insurance and covers the civil liability of the insured towards third parties. This means that if, as a result of fire, explosion, or bursting of water pipes at the insured location, bodily or financial damage is caused to third parties, the insurance company is obligated to compensate for the damages. According to

national laws, if fire spreads to neighboring buildings, the person whose negligence or recklessness started the fire is responsible for the damages inflicted on neighbors. Therefore, damages to the insured's own property as well as bodily and financial damages to neighboring buildings are compensated according to the terms of the insurance contract, and mainly through civil liability insurance arising from fire (based on current laws and the contractual clauses of the insurance).

3. Transfer of Civil Liability in Fire Insurance and Its Legal Nature

3.1 Formal Conditions for the Validity of the Insurance Contract

The proposal for fire insurance and liability arising therefrom is usually completed by the policyholder in the form of a written questionnaire and submitted to the insurer. The more accurately and comprehensively this questionnaire is completed, the more correctly the policy will be issued (Regulation No. 21 of the Supreme Council of Insurance, 1987). The insurance proposal is merely an offer and creates no obligation for the insurer; the insurer's acceptance depends on the risk assessment based on the information in the form and sometimes an expert inspection (Karimi, 2010). Until the policy is issued and the premium is paid, the insurer has no obligation, and in the event of an incident, the insurer bears no responsibility. Also, the insurer is not obliged to renew previous policies and may refuse to renew them; however, it is preferable to notify the policyholder so that they have an opportunity to find a replacement insurer (Karimi, 2010). According to Article 2 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policies, any part of the policyholder's proposal that is not accepted by the insurer and is announced in writing is not considered part of the insurer's obligations (Regulation No. 21 of the Supreme Council of Insurance, 1987). Laws precisely determine the format and content of insurance policies, and many

insurance companies use standard forms specific to fire insurance. In some insurances, such as life insurance, inclusion of certain standard articles and clauses is mandatory. In general, all policies must comply with insurance laws and related regulations (Mahdavi, 2019). In fire insurance, the general conditions (Regulation No. 21, approved by the Supreme Council of Insurance, 1987) and specific laws (the Insurance Law of 1937, the Civil Liability Law of 1960) govern the policies. According to Article 3 of the Insurance Law of 1937, items such as the date of conclusion of the contract, the names of the insurer and policyholder, the subject of insurance, the insured risk, the start and end dates of the insurance, the premium, the insurer's liability, and the beneficiary must be explicitly stated in the policy (Farjadi, 1997; Karimi, 2010). Also, the location of the insured property must be clearly specified in the policy, and any transfer of insured property without notifying the insurer and issuing an endorsement voids the insurer's obligation (Regulation No. 21, Supreme Council of Insurance). The inclusion of this information is necessary both for determining the parties' obligations and for risk management and reinsurance coverage for insurance companies (Karimi, 2010).

3.2 General Substantive Conditions for the Validity of the Insurance Contract

For the validity of the insurance contract, in addition to formal conditions, compliance with the general substantive conditions according to Article 190 of the Civil Code is mandatory (Khorrami, 1996; Shahidi, 1998, pp. 161 and 252): First, the conclusion of the insurance contract is subject to the general rules of contracts, and the existence of intention and consent of the parties for the formation of the contract is essential. The offer is usually made by the policyholder and acceptance is declared by the insurer. Second, both parties must have legal capacity; the policyholder must be of legal age, sane, and mature, and the insurer must

have a valid legal personality and the legal authority to issue the policy (Regulation 21 on Fire Insurance). Third, the subject of insurance must be completely clear and specified, and any ambiguity regarding the policyholder or the insured property invalidates the contract (Article 4 of the Insurance Law). Finally, the purpose of the transaction (the parties' motive) must be lawful. If an unlawful purpose is explicitly stated in the contract, the contract will be void (Khajeh Nouri, 1988, p. 72; Article 217 of the Civil Code).

3.3 Specific Substantive Conditions for the Validity of the Insurance Contract

For the validity of the insurance contract, in addition to the general substantive conditions, compliance with two specific substantive conditions is mandatory: First, the risk to be insured must exist at the time of the contract, and any ambiguity or uncertainty about it invalidates the contract; furthermore, the risk must be unforeseen, accidental, and outside the control of the parties (for example, fire). If the policyholder intentionally causes the risk, the insurance contract is not valid and compensation will not be paid (Insurance Law of 1937, Article 18). Second, the person purchasing the policy must have a real interest in the continued existence of the insured subject (the existence of insurable interest). Insurable interest includes ownership, usufruct right, mortgage, or liability towards the injured party. If the policyholder has no interest, the insurance contract becomes akin to betting or gambling and is invalid. These legal relationships are as follows:

- **Ownership of the property (whether joint or several):** The owner of any property (whether joint or several ownership) has the right to insure his property, as any legal disposition (including insurance) with respect to his share is permitted. The seller, too, until complete transfer of ownership or receipt of the price, can insure the property (Khajeh Nouri, 1988; Article 583 of the Civil Code).

- **Ownership of benefits or usufruct right:** The lessee, borrower, or holder of the right of usufruct and easement can insure the benefits of the leased or usufruct property. Insurance for the whole property in this case is only valid up to the extent of the benefits, and the rest of the insured capital belongs to the owner (Khajeh Nouri, 1988; Article 7 of the Insurance Law of 1937).

- **Mortgage right (mortgagee):** The mortgagee (secured creditor) has the right to insure the pledged property up to the amount of his claim. In case of an incident, the insurer pays the mortgagee up to the amount of his claim, and the remainder goes to the owner (Article 7 of the Insurance Law of 1937).

- **Liability towards the injured party:** A person who has legal or contractual responsibility to compensate others (for example, in civil liability insurance) has an insurable interest. The insurable interest must exist at the time of the contract; otherwise, the insurance contract is void.

3.4 The Duty of Good Faith for the Policyholder

The principle of good faith (*Uberrimae fidei*) is considered one of the fundamental principles of the insurance contract and is recognized as the essential distinguishing feature of insurance compared to other civil contracts. According to Article 9 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policies issued by the Supreme Council of Insurance (Regulation No. 21), the policyholder is obliged to provide the insurer with all necessary information about the subject of insurance with care and honesty. If the policyholder deliberately refrains from disclosing information or provides false information, the insurance contract will be void and ineffective, even if the concealed or false information had no effect on the occurrence of the incident; in this case, the amounts paid by the policyholder are not refunded, and the insurer may demand the remaining premium (Regulation No. 21,

Article 9). The importance of the principle of good faith is such that any disregard for it leads to the instability and invalidity of the insurance contract (Naseri, 2007). This principle is binding on both parties to the contract, and both parties must act in good faith even before the contract is concluded. In Iranian law, the legal effect of violating this principle depends on the existence or absence of malice. According to Article 12 of the Insurance Law, if the policyholder refrains from disclosing essential information or provides incorrect information, the insurance contract will be void, provided that such information affects the assessment of the insured risk. If there is no malice (intent), according to Article 13 of the same law, the contract is not void, and the insurer can only terminate the contract or adjust the premium; however, if an incident has occurred, compensation will be reduced in proportion to the premium paid. In comparative law, such as the legal systems of England and Indonesia, the duty of disclosure is the most fundamental duty of the policyholder, and the basis of the principle of good faith rests upon it. According to the doctrine of utmost good faith in England and Indonesia, if either party fails to observe the principle of good faith, the other party may terminate the contract. Full disclosure of facts, even at the pre-contractual stage, is the responsibility of the policyholder so that the insurer can accurately assess the risk and determine the conditions and premium (Shanty Ika Yuniartit, 2021). In Indonesia, Article 251 of the Commercial Code stipulates that any misrepresentation or failure to provide information about the conditions of the subject of insurance, if the insurer would not have concluded the contract if aware of the true facts, results in the contract being void. Furthermore, Article 32 of the Indonesian Insurance Law requires the policyholder to provide the insurer with sufficient information for anti-money laundering and counter-terrorism financing policies. As a result, compliance with the principle of good faith by the parties to the insurance contract—especially the policyholder—is a

fundamental condition for the validity of the contract and a prerequisite for enjoying insurance protection, and its violation may lead to invalidity or termination of the contract or reduction of the insurer's obligations (Regulation No. 21, Articles 9 and 12; Insurance Law, Articles 12 and 13; Naseri, 2007; Shanty Ika Yuniartit, 2021).

3.4.1 Good Faith of the Policyholder Before Issuance of the Policy

The foundation of the insurance contract is the insurer's accurate assessment of risk, which is only possible with the provision of correct and truthful information by the policyholder (Mary Kelly, 2017). For this purpose, insurance companies prepare an insurance proposal form that the policyholder is obliged to complete carefully. This form serves as the basis for the insurance contract, although before the issuance of the policy it does not create any legal obligation for the parties. Article 9 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policies emphasizes that the standard for providing information is the answers to the insurer's questions; therefore, if the policyholder has no knowledge of a particular question, he or she is not obliged to answer, and such ignorance is not considered malice. However, if the policyholder deliberately conceals previous insurance history or provides false information in response to a question, the insurer has the right to refuse compensation and even to void the contract. Therefore, insurance companies must raise all important matters through the questionnaire. If the insurer does not ask a question about an issue, the policyholder may assume that the matter is not important to the insurer. Nevertheless, if there are particular circumstances that are customarily considered important, the policyholder should disclose them even if the insurer has not asked; intentional non-disclosure, even without a question, may render the policy void (Amini, 2008, pp. 149-177).

3.4.2 Good Faith of the Policyholder During the Policy Period

The policyholder's duty of good faith is not limited to the pre-contractual stage; throughout the policy's validity, the policyholder is also obliged to act in good faith. According to Article 16 of the Insurance Law, the policyholder is required to immediately, or at the latest within ten days, notify the insurer of any aggravation or change in the risk, whether caused by his or her own act or not. In case of a change in risk, the insurer is entitled to adjust the premium or terminate the contract. Also, Article 15 of the Insurance Law obliges the policyholder to take the necessary precautions to prevent loss and, in the event of an incident, to inform the insurer at the earliest opportunity (no later than five days).

3.4.3 Good Faith of the Policyholder at the Time of Loss

At the time of loss, the policyholder must prove good faith by preventing the aggravation of the loss and rescuing the insured subject, promptly notifying the insurer of the incident, cooperating with the insurer in investigating and assessing the loss, preserving and reporting the state and nature of the damage, and providing the insurer with the opportunity for expert examination. In the legal systems of England and Indonesia, too, the policyholder is required to act honestly and disclose facts to the insurer in the event of loss, and if a fraudulent or false claim is made, the insurer has the right to void the contract and refuse payment of compensation (Shanty Ika Yuniartit, 2021).

3.5 Duty of Good Faith for the Insurer

In insurance contracts, the principle of good faith is of particular importance for both parties (the policyholder and the insurer), and its absence can lead to the invalidity of the contract. The significance of this principle for the insurer is vital not only from a moral

perspective but also for the protection of the policyholder's rights, since the policyholder usually, due to the technical nature of insurance, has less knowledge and expertise than the insurer. This obliges the insurer to maintain maximum transparency and honesty. The insurer must clearly state the terms, exclusions, and limitations of the policy in the contract and express them in a manner understandable to the policyholder (clarification of insurance conditions). The responsibility for the accurate and understandable inclusion of information lies with the insurer, and in case of ambiguity, interpretation will be in favor of the policyholder (Zeinali, 2020: 23). The insurer is obliged to keep the personal information and secrets of the policyholder confidential and not to disclose them to third parties without a legal order (Regulation on the Protection of Policyholders' Rights). Forced selling of insurance in any form is prohibited, and if it occurs, the insurance company is obliged to cancel the policy and refund the premium at the request of the policyholder. At the time of loss, the insurer must pay compensation to the policyholder with utmost honesty and necessary promptness, avoiding any obstruction or delay (Shanty Ika Yuniartit, 2021; Articles 1320 and 1338 of the Indonesian Civil Code). The insurer is required to clearly inform the policyholder about the consequences of misrepresentation or concealment of truth. The insurer should not request information from the policyholder beyond legal necessity. In summary, the principle of good faith is regarded as one of the fundamental foundations of insurance contracts, and any breach of it by the insurer or policyholder can have significant legal consequences such as the invalidity of the contract or civil liability.

3.6 Realization of the Policyholder's Civil Liability

Coverage for financial liability arising from fire, explosion, and the bursting of water and sewage pipes in relation to neighbors is provided according to Article 13 of the

General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy and the Civil Liability Law of 1960, and based on the written request of the policyholder. The subject of this insurance is the compensation of financial damages incurred by adjacent properties and their belongings due to the aforementioned risks. In the event of an incident and damage to neighbors, the insurer is obliged to compensate for the damages up to the coverage limit specified in the policy, and payment is made directly to the injured party or their legal heirs. Furthermore, the amount of compensation is determined by the insurer's expert, and the insurer's liability limit usually does not exceed fifty percent of the total insured sum. If several neighbors are damaged, the payment amount is divided among them in proportion to the damages incurred. The policyholder also, without the insurer's consent, does not have the right to accept liability toward claimants or to agree on the amount of damages (Article 13 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy; Civil Liability Law of 1960).

3.7 Legal Nature of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire

Civil liability insurance arising from fire compensates the policyholder's liability towards third parties for financial and bodily damages, medical expenses, and legal claims related to covered incidents (fire, explosion, and bursting of pipes) (Ofoghi, 2013, p. 32). This type of insurance plays a fundamental role in providing peace of mind and supporting economic and social activities, since the policyholder is assured that in case of damage to third parties, the insurance company is obliged to compensate for the loss. The main difference between civil liability insurance and property insurance is that in property insurance, the subject of insurance is specific and determined, and damages to the policyholder's property are compensated; but in liability insurance, damages incurred by third parties are covered, and usually this insurance is issued following fire insurance. Furthermore, in

civil liability insurance, a tripartite relationship exists between the insurer, the policyholder, and the third party, and the principle of subrogation is applied in cases where the third party is at fault for the incident. From a legal perspective, the insurer's obligation in this policy is not in favor of the third party; rather, the insurer's liability is subsidiary and dependent on the policyholder's obligation, and the insurer merely substitutes the policyholder in paying compensation to the third party. Therefore, the third party merely benefits from this insurance, but is not considered a direct beneficiary of the contract.

3.7.1 The Theory of Obligation in Favor of Third Parties

An obligation in favor of a third party is an exception to the principle of relativity of contracts, according to which, pursuant to Article 231 of the Civil Code, the effects of a contract are generally limited to the parties and their legal successors, except in cases such as Article 196, which also provides for the possibility of creating an obligation in favor of a third party (Asadpour, 2016). In this structure, the obligor creates a right for a third-party beneficiary, even though the latter is not among the main parties to the contract. With regard to the legal nature of civil liability insurance arising from fire, some jurists believe that this type of insurance constitutes an obligation in favor of a third party; meaning that the insurance company undertakes, in favor of the injured party (the third party), to compensate for the damages caused by the policyholder. Regarding the details of this institution, there are two major approaches: the first group considers the third party's will effective in the creation of the obligation, while the second group regards it as merely subject to the will of the main parties to the contract.

3.7.2 The Proposal or Dual-Contract Theory

This theory emphasizes the involvement of the third party's will in the creation of the right. According to this view, initially a right is created in favor of one of the contracting parties (the stipulator), and then this right is offered to the third party; only upon acceptance by the third party does the final obligation arise. In other words, this process results from two contracts: one is the main contract between the parties, and the other is a contract formed between the stipulator and the third party (Asadpour, 2016). Nevertheless, the acceptance of this theory in explaining the nature of civil liability insurance is problematic. First, Article 231 of the Civil Code provides for the obligation in favor of a third party as an exception to the principle of relativity of contracts, and if everything were subject to the third party's acceptance, such an exception would not be necessary. Second, if the third party's acceptance is considered a condition for the creation of the obligation, no right would exist for him until acceptance, while the intention of the insurance contract is for the insurer's obligation in favor of the third party to be created at the time of contract formation, not after the third party's acceptance. Third, if the policyholder is considered the principal party to the second contract, the beneficiary (the injured party) would only have the right to recourse against the policyholder, whereas the purpose of the insurance contract is to create an obligation for the insurer toward the third party, not just the policyholder. Therefore, this theory does not align with the true intention of the parties in civil liability insurance contracts.

3.7.3 The Unauthorized Agency (Management of Another's Property) Theory

This theory also emphasizes the involvement of the third party's will and considers the promisee as an unauthorized manager who undertakes an obligation for the benefit of a third party. In this view, the obligation is created for the third party from the time of contract formation, and he can directly claim

his right, and the death or legal incapacity of either party does not nullify this right; even the heirs of the beneficiary may confirm it (Mohaqqeq Damad et al., 2013). However, this theory also faces difficulties in explaining the nature of civil liability insurance arising from fire. First, in the management of another's property, the manager acts on behalf of the owner, but in the insurance contract, the policyholder is not merely an intermediary and is also a beneficiary. Second, the manager in the management of another's property must recover his expenses from the owner, whereas the policyholder does not have such a right against the beneficiary. Third, the manager in unauthorized agency has no right to terminate the arrangement, but the policyholder in an obligation in favor of a third party can demand execution or termination of the obligation from the insurer. Fourth, in unauthorized agency, the obligation is imposed by law on the owner, while in an obligation in favor of a third party, no obligation is imposed on the beneficiary. Fifth, unauthorized agency is provided in the law to protect the incapable, but in an obligation in favor of a third party, such a presumption does not exist. Sixth, in unauthorized agency, an obligation may arise to the detriment of the owner, while in an obligation in favor of a third party, the obligation is only to the benefit of the beneficiary (Mohaqqeq Damad et al., 2013).

3.7.4 The Unilateral Declaration of Will Theory (Ijā')

According to this theory, the obligation in favor of a third party is created as a unilateral act (Ijā') without the need for the third party's acceptance. In other words, the realization of the obligation is achieved solely by the will of the policyholder and the insurer, and the agreement of the third party is not necessary. However, this view has been criticized, since in reality, the obligation in favor of a third party results from the agreement of two wills (the insurer and the policyholder) and cannot be regarded as

arising solely from one will (Asadpour, 2016).

3.7.5 The Theory of Direct Obligation Arising from the Contract

According to this theory, the obligation in favor of a third party is the result of the contract concluded between the insurer and the policyholder, and creates a direct right for the third party without the need for the will or involvement of the third party. This right is established from the time of the base contract's conclusion, and neither the death nor legal incapacity of any of the parties or the third party affects it; in the event of annulment of the contract, this right is also extinguished. The main criticism of this theory is that it merely refers to the creation of a right for the third party and does not clearly explain its legal origin. Nevertheless, it seems that explaining the nature of the institution of an obligation in favor of a third party based on this theory most closely aligns with the legal realities of Iran and the intent of the contracting parties. However, it must be emphasized that in civil liability insurance arising from fire, this institution is not in the sense of an obligation in favor of a third party, but rather the third party merely benefits from it (Asadpour, 2016).

3.8 Legal Nature of Fire Insurance

In fire insurance, the legal relationship is typically established between two parties, namely the policyholder and the insurer, and the main objective of the policyholder is to secure compensation for possible damages. The insurer's obligation is to pay compensation for potential damages to the policyholder in exchange for receiving the premium. In other words, fire insurance is considered a bilateral contract, which is concluded through the mutual agreement of the parties' wills and complies with the substantive and formal requirements for the validity of insurance contracts. However, if the policyholder seeks coverage for civil liability toward neighbors, the contract, in

terms of parties and nature, may become similar to civil liability insurance arising from fire and may be governed by its specific rules.

4. Review of Contractual Clauses in Fire Insurance and Their Role in the Transfer of Liability

4.1 Insurance Premium

In an insurance contract, each party has rights and obligations, and fulfillment of these obligations is essential for the validity of the insurance contract (Zeinali, 2020: 25). Insurance is a commutative contract in which the policyholder, by paying the premium, gains peace of mind, and the insurer undertakes the obligation to compensate for potential losses. However, the fulfillment of the insurer's obligation is conditional upon payment of the premium by the policyholder; in other words, after the contract is concluded, its validity depends on the payment of the premium. Furthermore, if the insurance is concluded by an agent or attorney, the responsibility for payment remains with the policyholder. According to Articles 3 and 7 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policies issued by the Supreme Council of Insurance (Regulation No. 21, enacted in 1987), the validity of the policy and the insurer's obligation commence after payment of the first installment of the premium, and the policyholder remains obligated to pay the remaining installments, unless another start date has been agreed. Also, according to Article 7 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire, enacted in 1960, the existence of insurance coverage and its resulting effects begin from 24:00 on the day the premium is paid, unless another date is specified in the policy. Despite the legislator's explicit statement that the insurer's obligation begins after payment of the first installment, an appropriate sanction for non-payment of subsequent installments is not specified in the regulation, and it would have been preferable if the status of automatic termination of the contract in such

cases had been stated more explicitly (derived from Regulation No. 21).

4.1.1 Determining the Amount of the Premium and the Possibility of Its Adjustment

Accurate determination of the premium is of great importance, as balancing the amount of compensation with the received premiums ensures the survival of insurance companies. The determination of the insurance rate is not at the discretion of the insurance companies; after a rate is proposed by the company, it must be reviewed by the Central Insurance of Iran and, upon approval by the Supreme Council of Insurance, communicated to the company. After this stage, the insurance company can issue policies at the approved rate. The insured amount and the policy validity period must also be determined by the policyholder so that the insurer can calculate the premium rate. Multiple factors, such as the level of risk of the capital, environmental conditions, and even the country's economic circumstances (such as increases in the price of raw materials), influence the determination of the premium rate; for instance, increased replacement costs of capital necessitate higher insurance rates so that, in the event of a loss, the policyholder's capital can be restored. In calculating the fire insurance premium, two main methods are considered, one of which is the daily-rate method. In this method, if the policyholder wishes to terminate the policy before the end of the term, the insurer is obliged to calculate the premium rate on a daily basis.

$$\text{Daily Insurance Premium} = (\text{Duration} / 365) \times (\text{Rate} / 1000) \times \text{Insurance Capital}$$

Calculating insurance premiums using the short-term method:

$$\text{Short-Term Insurance Premium} = \text{Short-Term Percentage} \times (\text{Rate} / 1000) \times \text{Insurance Capital}$$

4.1.2 Method and Timing of Premium Payment

The premium is one of the main elements of the insurance contract, and the policyholder is obligated to pay it, while the insurer is committed to compensating potential losses. The validity of the insurance contract commences from the time of payment of the first premium installment, and the default is payment in cash, unless otherwise agreed by the parties (Article 14 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policy, Regulation No. 21). Installment payment of the premium is also possible upon agreement, and the policyholder is required to pay the installments on their due dates; otherwise, the insurer may refuse to compensate for losses. If the premium payment is made by issuing a check and the check is not cleared, or if the loss occurs before clearance, the insurer is not obligated to pay the compensation; because the check is merely a payment instrument and non-clearance means the premium has not been paid. Regarding bills of exchange and promissory notes, some jurists believe that issuing these instruments is a kind of novation and is considered as receipt of payment, but this view has been criticized, and in Iranian law, the mere issuance of commercial instruments such as promissory notes and bills of exchange does not constitute payment of the premium unless they are collected (Al-Sheikh, 2005: 149-189). If the bill or promissory note is payable at a future date and the loss occurs before maturity, the insurer must compensate the loss and later claim the payment on the instrument. In summary, the commencement of the insurer's obligation is conditional upon payment of the first premium installment, unless otherwise agreed by the parties, and if payment is agreed to be deferred, the insurer is obliged to fulfill its commitment to the policyholder.

4.1.3 Sanction for Non-Payment of Premium

There is no explicit provision in the Insurance Law regarding the sanction for non-payment of the premium; however, Article 1 of the Insurance Law (enacted 1937) makes the insurer's compensation conditional upon payment of the premium. Additionally, Article 7 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy, Regulation No. 21, considers the validity of the policy and the commencement of the insurer's obligation to be dependent on payment of the first premium installment. If the premium is not paid, the insurer is not obliged to compensate for losses. Payment of the first installment is a condition for the commencement of the policy's validity, and payment of the remaining installments is the responsibility and debt of the policyholder. One contractual solution for ensuring premium payment is the inclusion of a condition subsequent or a termination right for the insurer in the specific conditions of the policy, so that, in the event of non-payment, the contract is automatically terminated or the insurer may terminate it. The insurer may also terminate the policy by issuing a notice of termination according to Article 21 of the General Conditions. If the premium is paid in installments and only the first installment is paid, and during the period of non-payment of subsequent installments a loss occurs, the insurer compensates the loss in proportion to the premium paid; this conforms to the principle of proportional premium and protects the rights of both parties (Regulation No. 21; Zeinali, 2020).

4.2 Condition of Notification of the Incident

In insurance contracts, the policyholder is obliged, in the event of an incident, to immediately notify the insurer so that the insurer can examine the effects of the incident and determine the extent of its obligation (Zeinali, 2020, p. 29). The legislator has remained silent regarding the method of notification; however, according to Article 23 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy (Regulation No. 21),

the policyholder must notify the insurer no later than five days after becoming aware of the incident; otherwise, the insurer bears no responsibility, unless the policyholder proves that failure to notify in due time was due to reasons beyond their control. The purpose of this requirement is to preserve the evidence and traces of the incident for accurate assessment of the loss. Delay in notification may lead to the impairment of the insurer's rights and even result in the policyholder being deprived of compensation (Al-Sheikh, 2005). However, the law allows the policyholder to be exempted from this sanction if, for a justified reason, timely notification was not possible. According to Article 15 of the Insurance Law, this obligation mainly rests with the policyholder, but in cases where insurance is in favor of a third party, the beneficiary or even other persons may also notify the insurer of the incident. The main purpose is for the insurer to be informed in order to protect its rights, not merely to observe the formalities of notification (Regulation No. 21; Al-Sheikh, 2005).

4.3 Condition of Notification of the Circumstances of the Fire

The policyholder, in addition to notifying the occurrence of fire damage, must, within ten days at most, notify the insurer of the details of the incident, a list of salvaged items, their new location, and the approximate amount of the loss. This information helps the insurer to investigate the cause of the incident (whether due to negligence, fault, or willful misconduct by the policyholder, legal heirs, or third parties) and to determine its own responsibility. Furthermore, the policyholder is obliged to, within fifteen days after being informed of the incident, submit to the insurer a list of existing, destroyed, and damaged items and, if requested by the insurer, their value before the incident, so that the insurer's liability and the possibility of applying the proportional value rule can be determined (Regulation No. 21; Yamini, 2003, p. 116).

4.4 Condition of the Insurer's Access for Inspection

The policyholder is obliged to enable the insurer and its experts to inspect and examine the scene of the incident. Refusal to cooperate may be regarded as an indication of the policyholder's liability and may result in the denial of compensation (Yamini, 2003, p. 116). According to paragraph 4 of Article 3 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire (enacted in 1960), the policyholder's cooperation with the insurer's expert for inspection of the incident location is mandatory.

4.5 Condition of Avoiding the Removal of Evidence

The policyholder must not remove or alter the traces of damage before the insurer's assessment or make changes to the insured subject that would make it difficult to determine the cause of the incident or to evaluate the loss—unless such changes have been approved by the insurer or are intended to reduce the loss. This requirement helps the insurer to properly assess the extent of the loss. The insurer is also obliged to pay the compensation within a maximum of four weeks after receiving the required documents (Yamini, 2003, p. 117). According to paragraph 3 of Article 3 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire (enacted in 1960), making changes without the insurer's permission is only permissible in special circumstances.

4.6 Condition of Reasonable Protection of the Insured Object

One of the essential requirements in an insurance contract is the existence of an "insurable interest" for the policyholder, meaning that he or she must benefit from the continued existence of the insured subject. Accordingly, the policyholder is obliged to take reasonable actions and precautions, according to customary practice, to prevent the occurrence of an incident and to prevent

the spread of loss. The insurer's obligation only covers unforeseeable losses, and losses caused by the policyholder's willful misconduct or negligence are not compensable (Article 15 of the Insurance Law; Zeinali, 2020, p. 29). According to Article 15 of the Insurance Law, the policyholder must exercise the care that he would customarily exercise over his own property with respect to the insured object, and, in the event of an incident, take the necessary measures to prevent the spread and development of the loss. Expenses incurred by the policyholder to prevent the development of the loss (even if not successful) are the responsibility of the insurer; however, these costs must be proportionate to the incident, and in case of dispute, the court will decide (Yamini, 2003, p. 115). According to paragraph 3 of Article 3 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire (enacted in 1960), the policyholder is obliged to take the necessary measures to prevent the extension of the loss, but without the insurer's permission, is not entitled to make changes that would create ambiguity in the loss assessment, unless to reduce the loss or protect the public interest. Furthermore, losses arising from the policyholder's actions to prevent the spread and development of fire (such as the evacuation or demolition of a building to extinguish the fire) are covered by the insurer (Article 21 of the Insurance Law). However, costs incurred to prevent the occurrence of the incident before the risk arises are the responsibility of the policyholder, and the insurer has no obligation in this regard (Mirzaei Abdalyousefi, 2014).

4.7 Condition of Non-Acceptance of Liability by the Policyholder

In fire insurance, compensation by the insurer is carried out based on the contractual clauses. However, in cases where compensation of a third party is involved, the policyholder must not accept his or her civil liability or make any commitment to the

claimant without the consent of the insurer, as such action may affect the insurer's rights and alter its legal responsibility. The insurer's liability is subject to the liability of the policyholder and only arises when the policyholder's liability has been determined by the competent authority. Therefore, arbitrary acceptance of liability by the policyholder is invalid (Article 4 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire, enacted in 1960). Moreover, any settlement between the policyholder and the injured third party without the insurer's consent is not binding on the insurer, since the insurer is only obligated to pay compensation up to the contractual limit, and the authority to settle with the injured party principally belongs to the insurer. If the policyholder, without coordinating with the insurer, settles with the injured party, such a settlement will not create an obligation for the insurer and is only effective up to the extent of the policyholder's own commitments.

4.8 Condition of Notification of Aggravation of Risk

One of the fundamental requirements in insurance contracts is the policyholder's transparency and honesty in providing information related to the insured subject. Accordingly, if, after the conclusion of the insurance contract, the circumstances of the insured subject change in a way that increases the insured risk, the policyholder is obliged to immediately and without delay inform the insurer. This requirement is explicitly stated in Article 18 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policies issued by the Supreme Council of Insurance (Regulation No. 21, enacted on 1987/11/18). According to this article, if the policyholder himself takes an action or performs an act that aggravates the risk, he must immediately notify the insurer. If the aggravation of risk is not due to a direct act of the policyholder but he becomes aware of it, he must notify the insurer within ten days at the latest. After notification of the aggravation of risk, the

insurer may continue the contract under the previous conditions, or recalculate the premium according to the new risk and collect the difference from the policyholder; if the policyholder agrees, the contract will continue. If the parties do not agree on the new premium amount, or if the policyholder does not accept it, the contract is considered terminated (termination of the contract). It should be noted that the insurer may also claim the additional premium for the duration of the aggravated risk until the termination or expiration of the contract. It appears that the purpose of this condition is to prevent fundamental changes in the risk of the contract's subject without the insurer's knowledge, to maintain the balance of consideration (premium and insurance coverage), and to ensure the continuity of the principle of utmost good faith in insurance. In Iranian insurance law, the right to reduce the risk is not anticipated, while it is expected that in the event of a reduction of risk, the policyholder should also be able to request a reduction in premium or more favorable terms. This is one of the current shortcomings of Iranian insurance law and requires amendment to establish a fairer balance between the interests of the insurer and the policyholder. In general, the condition of notification of aggravation of risk guarantees proper risk management for the insurer and continued equitable coverage for the policyholder. Proper implementation of this condition leads to transparency, reduces disputes, and prevents complex claims in the loss compensation process.

4.9 Condition of Non-Multiplicity of Policies and Double Insurance

In insurance law, the principle of multiple insurance refers to the conclusion of several policies for the same property, the same risk, the same period, and in favor of the same beneficiary. This is not necessarily contrary to the principle of indemnity, and in many cases, such as joint and consortium insurance, the participation of several insurers in covering a single risk is desirable

and common (Karimi, 2010; Yamini, 2003). In joint insurance, several insurers each assume a percentage of the risk according to their financial capacity and receive and pay a share of the premium and loss in the same proportion. This mechanism, especially in large insurance and major industries, increases capacity and reduces risk for the insurance system. The responsibility for paying the loss in such cases is proportional to each insurer's share in the contract. Double insurance occurs when the same property is insured for the same risk, for the same duration, and with several different insurance companies, and the beneficiary in all policies is the same person. Therefore, if there is unity of the subject insured (specific property), unity of the insured risk, unity of policy term, and unity of beneficiary, double insurance is realized. In such cases, the policyholder must notify the insurers (Article 17 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policy). In the event of a loss, the responsibility of the insurers is divided in proportion to the amount each has insured, and the policyholder may not, in total, recover more than the actual amount of the loss from all the insurers. The principle of indemnity prevents making a profit or gaining a double benefit from insurance. Accordingly, if there is bad faith and fraudulent intent on the part of the policyholder, all the policies will be void and none of the insurers will be liable for payment of compensation (Article 22 of the General Conditions). Therefore, in the absence of bad faith, only the principle of indemnity is observed, and the loss is divided proportionally, with no possibility of receiving more than the actual amount of the damage. Article 8 of the General Conditions of Civil Liability Insurance Arising from Fire, and Article 17 of the General Conditions of Fire Insurance Policy all stipulate that the insurer's obligation is proportional to its share of the total insured amount. In summary, issuing several policies for one property, provided the policyholder does not intend to defraud, is valid; however, compensation is only paid up to the actual

amount of the loss. In joint insurance, the share of each insurer in paying compensation is determined by agreement, and in the event of a loss, the lead or senior insurer manages the collection and division of the loss. In the case of double insurance with fraudulent intent, all policies are void, and the insurer has no obligation to pay compensation.

4.10 Condition of Declaring the True Value of the Capital

Declaring the true value of the capital is one of the essential conditions in property and indemnity insurance. The importance of this condition lies in the fact that the value of the capital declared by the policyholder serves as the basis for calculating the premium and for the insurer's obligation to compensate any potential loss. According to Article 8 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy (Regulation No. 21, enacted in 1987), compensation under no circumstances shall exceed the amount of loss suffered by the policyholder in respect of the insured subject at the time of the loss. Article 12 of the same regulation further stipulates that the payable loss must not exceed the difference in value of the insured subject before and after the incident, and in the event of total loss, must not exceed the insured amount. This condition is established in accordance with the principle of indemnity, so that insurance is not used as a means of profit-making or earning additional income, and only the actual loss of the policyholder is compensated. With respect to the sanction, Article 11 of the Insurance Law (enacted in 1937) states that if the policyholder, with fraudulent intent, declares the insured capital at a value higher than its true value, the insurance contract is void and the paid premium is not refundable. However, if there is no bad faith or fraud, the contract remains valid and the insurer will compensate for the actual loss, although any excess premium paid will not be refunded.

4.10.1 Over-Insurance

In fire insurance, if the policyholder insures his or her property for an amount exceeding its actual value, an over-insurance situation arises. This can occur either with fraudulent intent or without it, and each case has different legal consequences. If the policyholder or his representative, at the time of concluding the insurance contract, knowingly and with the intent to defraud, declares the insured value higher than the fair value, according to Article 11 of the Insurance Law, the insurance contract is void and of no effect, and the paid premium is not refundable. In such a case, even if an incident occurs and loss is sustained, the insurer has no obligation to pay compensation and the policyholder has no right to claim for losses, as the insurance contract is void and there is no basis for indemnification (Yamini, 2003, p. 118). If over-insurance occurs without bad faith or fraudulent intent (for example, due to error by the policyholder or due to a decrease in the actual value of property after the policy is issued), then in the event of an incident, the insurer is only obligated to pay up to the actual value of the property at the time of the loss, not the higher declared value. In this situation, the policyholder is only entitled to compensation equal to the actual loss, and receiving more than the actual loss is prohibited—even if extra premium has been paid. The return of excess premium is generally not possible, but no right to excess compensation is created for the policyholder. This rule is based on the principle of indemnity in insurance: the aim of insurance is to compensate actual loss, not to provide profit or gain for the policyholder; thus, the policyholder should not be in a better position after the incident and indemnification than before. Accordingly, in liability insurance (such as civil liability insurance arising from fire), over-insurance is not applicable, as the subject of insurance is the policyholder's liability toward third parties and the insurer's obligation is determined by the insured amount. However, in fire insurance where the subject is property, this issue becomes significant.

4.10.2 Under-Insurance

Under-insurance arises when the policyholder, at the time of concluding the insurance contract, declares the actual value of the property to be less than the market value, and the policy and premium are calculated based on this value. As a result, the insurer is only obligated to indemnify in proportion to the insured amount versus the actual value. This rule, referred to as the "proportional value rule" or "principle of proportional value," is set forth by the legislator in Article 10 of the Insurance Law. The principle of indemnity in property insurance requires that the policyholder is compensated only up to the actual loss and in proportion to the insured value; he or she is not entitled to receive compensation exceeding the declared amount. Therefore, if the policyholder insures for an amount lower than the actual value, in the event of a loss, the insurer will only compensate proportionally, and the policyholder must personally bear part of the loss.

$$\text{Payable Compensation} = \left(\frac{\text{Insured Amount}}{\text{Actual Value at the Time of Incident}} \right) \times \text{Incurred Loss Amount}$$

For example, if the actual capital is 60 million tomans and the policyholder has insured only 40 million tomans, and a total loss occurs, the insurer will compensate only two-thirds of the loss. Under-insurance is to the detriment of the policyholder, and the insurer is only obligated in proportion to the declared value. The common reason for under-insurance in Iran is book value assessment, disregard for inflation, and an increase in the actual value of assets. The usual solution for remedying the effects of under-insurance is to issue endorsements for capital increases in line with inflation or use an indexation clause, which must be agreed upon by both parties. According to regulations, the policyholder is obliged to notify the insurer of any significant reduction in value so that the policy capital can be adjusted. The rule of under-insurance applies only to property insurance (such as fire insurance) and does not apply to life or

liability insurance, in which the insurer is obligated to pay the capital stated in the policy, and the principle of proportional value is not applicable.

4.11 Condition of Proof of Inventory

In fire insurance and other property insurance, the burden of proving the existence and actual value of the insured property at the time of the incident lies with the policyholder. According to the regulations, the policyholder is required to provide the insurer, within a maximum of ten days after becoming aware of the incident, with information including the details of the incident, a list of salvaged items, their new location, and the approximate amount of the loss. The issuance of the insurance policy and even the initial inspection by the insurer does not mean confirmation of the existence or actual value of the insured property at the time of the incident. Therefore, the policyholder must prove that the insured property existed at the insured location at the moment of the incident and that it suffered damage (Parsa, 2019, p. 216). This condition reflects the principle of indemnity in property insurance and prevents the policyholder from claiming or receiving more than the actual loss suffered. In some contracts, it is stipulated that a detailed list of property and its separate valuation, confirmed by the insurer and attached to the policy, must be provided.

4.12 The Extent of the Insurer's Obligations

In fire insurance, the insurer undertakes to compensate the loss sustained by the insured property up to the amount specified in the policy and subject to the existence and actual value of the property at the time of the incident being established. According to the principle of indemnity, the policyholder is only compensated to the extent of restoration to the pre-incident status, and insurance should not result in the policyholder's gain. Therefore, receiving an amount in excess of

the actual loss is legally and ethically unjustifiable.

If the insured amount is equal to the actual value, the loss will be fully compensated. Otherwise, if the insured amount is less than the actual value, the underinsurance rule is applied, and the insurer only pays compensation in proportion to the declared capital. In any event, payment of compensation must not exceed the insured amount stated in the policy, even if the actual value of the property is higher or the loss suffered is greater. In civil liability insurance arising from fire, regarding third parties, the insurer undertakes to pay compensation for bodily injury (death, disability, medical expenses) and property damage to third parties up to the coverage limits purchased by the policyholder, which are stated in the policy for each section (medical, bodily, property) separately. The insurer generally specifies two types of coverage limits: the first is the aggregate limit for the entire insurance period, and the second is the per person or per occurrence limit. After payment of compensation, the amount paid is deducted from the principal coverage, and until the expiration of the policy, the insurer's liability only remains up to the remaining coverage.

4.12.1 The Extent of the Insurer's Obligations Regarding Changes in the Amount of Diyyeh (Blood Money)

In liability insurance, particularly in the context of bodily injuries and payment of diyyeh (blood money), a fundamental challenge arises concerning the annual increase in the amount of diyyeh, which can affect the insurer's level of obligation. According to Iranian legal regulations, the amount of diyyeh is determined each year by the Judiciary and forms the basis for the execution of judicial decisions and for the payment of compensation by the insurer (Babaei, 2018, p. 297). In liability insurance policies, the insured sum and the insurer's coverage limit are specified based on the

diyyeh rate at the time the contract is concluded. If the incident, the court ruling, and the payment of diyyeh all occur within the same year, the insurer fulfills its obligation accordingly and no dispute arises. However, when there is an increase in the diyyeh rate between the occurrence of the incident and the payment of diyyeh, a legal issue emerges. Under the Compulsory Third-Party Liability Insurance Law for Motor Vehicle Accidents, the insurer's obligation to pay diyyeh is based on the rate at the time of payment (yawm al-ada'); that is, if the judgment is executed and diyyeh is paid in a year other than the year the contract was concluded, the insurer is required to pay diyyeh at the new rate and cannot rely on the coverage limit stated in the policy (Babaei, 2018, p. 297). This rule is specific to third-party liability insurance and is explicitly stated in the Compulsory Insurance Law. In other civil liability insurances, including fire insurance, the insurer's obligation to pay compensation is limited only up to the amount stated in the policy, and the insurer has no responsibility to pay in excess of this amount in the event of an increase in the diyyeh rate (ibid). Therefore, in motor vehicle third-party liability insurance, the insurer's obligation for payment of diyyeh is based on the rate at the time of payment (yawm al-ada'), even if it exceeds the coverage limit of the policy (Compulsory Motor Vehicle Civil Liability Insurance Law, Article 8), but in other liability and fire insurances, the insurer's obligation is limited only up to the coverage purchased in the policy, and the insurer has no responsibility for amounts in excess of this (Babaei, 2018, p. 297).

4.12.2 Insurer's Obligations in Payment of Compensation to the Mortgagee

If there is a mortgage contract between two persons, the mortgagee (creditor) is considered to have an insurable interest due to his or her stake in the preservation of the pledged property and may insure the property. However, the amount of

compensation the mortgagee is entitled to receive is limited solely to the amount of the debt owed by the mortgagor (debtor), and insurance cannot result in the mortgagee's enrichment. Although the mortgagee has the right to insure the entire property, in the event of a loss, he or she is entitled to receive compensation only up to the amount of the claim. If the mortgagee has not taken out independent insurance and compensation is paid by the insurer to the mortgagor, the mortgagee may only recover the debt by requiring the mortgagor to fulfill his or her obligation, because according to Article 791 of the Civil Code, the mortgagee does not have a direct legal position in the insurance contract, and his or her relationship is contractual (Articles 771 and 791 of the Civil Code). Also, according to Article 19 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy, the insurer must observe the legal rights of the mortgagee up to its maximum obligation, provided that the rights of the mortgagee have been notified to the insurer.

4.12.3 Circumstances Reducing the Amount of Compensation Paid

In certain cases, the amount of compensation paid by the insurer is reduced: First, if the loss results from the action of the policyholder, their legal successors, or household family members, compensation is reduced in proportion to the degree of fault. Second, if at the time of concluding the fire insurance contract, the policyholder, without bad faith, refrains from disclosing necessary information or provides false information, compensation will be reduced in proportion to the premium paid and what should have been paid had full disclosure been made. Third, if the insured property is already covered by another policy, such as a cargo insurance policy, compensation is first paid under the prior policy, and any remainder (if any remains) is paid according to the fire insurance policy. Fourth, if the property is insured for less than its actual value, the rule of proportional value (principle of underinsurance) will be applied. Finally, if

the policyholder could have prevented the aggravation of the loss but was negligent, compensation will be reduced according to the degree of the policyholder's fault (Yamini, 2003, p. 120). According to Article 26 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy of the High Council of Insurance, enacted 1987/11/18 (Regulation No. 21), the insurer is obliged to settle and pay compensation no later than four weeks after receiving all documents and evidence required for determining the scope of liability and the amount of loss.

4.12.4 Method of Compensation for Losses

In fire insurance, the method of compensation for losses is, according to Article 25 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy of the High Council of Insurance (Regulation No. 21), at the discretion of the insurer. The insurer may acquire, repair, or replace the damaged or salvaged property. This decision must be communicated to the policyholder in writing and within no more than 30 days after receipt of the required documents. The policyholder is also required to provide, within 15 days of being informed of the incident, a list of existing, destroyed, and damaged property, and, upon the insurer's request, the value of those items (Regulation No. 21, Article 25). Methods of compensation may include cash payment, which is still the usual approach for commercial losses. Payment for repairs is also possible, especially in motor vehicle insurance, or by replacement, commonly seen in household or glass insurance, and finally, restoration to the original state, where the insurer undertakes full reconstruction of the property. However, this last method rarely occurs in practice unless specifically stipulated in the policy (Ofoghi, 2013, p. 85). The application of the last two methods (replacement and restoration) is possible only if expressly provided in the policy. In certain exceptional cases, even in the absence of the insurer's explicit liability, compensation may be paid out of good faith or for customer relations

reasons (Ofoghi, 2013). According to Article 27 of the same regulation, the insurer may, in special circumstances, refuse compensation or reduce the amount in proportion to the policyholder's or their successor's degree of fault; for example, if the incident is due to the policyholder's fault or if the policyholder has failed to fulfill their obligations under Article 23, and this failure has led to increased loss or impairment of the insurer's rights (Regulation No. 21, Article 27).

4.13 Condition of Litigation Management

In civil liability insurance, the defense of claims brought against the insured is often assigned to the insurer in order to best protect the rights of both parties, since the primary beneficiary of the compensation payment is the insurer and the motivation for effective defense may be weaker on the part of the insured. Accordingly, in some contracts (such as Article 6 of the General Conditions of Professional Medical Liability Insurance Policies, High Council of Insurance, 1998), the insurer is entitled to assume the defense of the claim at its own expense, and the insured is obligated to authorize the selection of counsel and provide the necessary documents and evidence to the insurer. The insured's failure to cooperate in this respect may result in liability to compensate the insurer for damages incurred (Babaei, 2010: 183). The right of access to the courts is recognized in Principle 34 of the Iranian Constitution and in ordinary laws such as Article 36 of the Insurance Act of 1937 and Article 28 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy (Regulation No. 21, 1987). According to these provisions, the statute of limitations for bringing claims arising from insurance is two years from the date of the incident or the expiration of the policy, after which the claim will not be heard. This approach has also been emphasized in judicial decisions (Central Insurance of Iran, 2021). If a third party files a lawsuit against the insured, the insured may, to avoid prolonged litigation, join the insurer to the proceedings as a third party

under the terms of the insurance contract. Upon establishing the liability of the insured, the court may also order the insurer to pay damages in proportion to the contractual obligations. This action facilitates compensation and reduces the duration of litigation. In cases where the injured party, under the rules of civil liability, claims compensation directly from the insured and receives payment, the insured may subsequently, according to the insurance contract, seek reimbursement from the insurer. In this process, the insurance company, considering the terms of the policy, risk coverage, and other contractual conditions, will review the entitlement of the insured and, if the conditions are met, will make the payment. If the insurer refuses to pay compensation, the insured is compelled to file a claim with the competent authorities to establish the insurer's liability. It should be noted that if the insured is found liable to the third-party claimant, the insurance company may, as a third party, object to the issued judgment (Babaei, 2010). Moreover, settlement by the insured with the injured third party, without the insurer's consent, is legally ineffective under the Insurance Act, and claiming this amount requires proof in court. In principle, the injured party should, based on the rules of civil liability, seek recourse from the liable party (the insured), but in some legal systems such as France, the possibility of a direct claim against the insurer is recognized (Babaei, 2010: 188). In French law, following legislative reforms and judicial precedent, the injured party's direct action against the insurer is now the rule, and the Insurance Act of 1930 expressly provides that the insurer cannot fulfill its obligations by paying anyone other than the injured party without the latter's consent. Similarly, such direct actions are accepted under English law, but in the form of subrogation from the insured, and the insurer may raise the same defenses against the injured party as against the insured. Nevertheless, under French legal principles, a claim by the injured party against the insurer must be brought within the

framework of the insurance contract and is subject to contractual limitations and coverage limits (Babaei, 2010). In Iranian law, the Insurance Act does not explicitly provide for the possibility of a direct claim by the injured party against the insurer. Nevertheless, to protect the injured party's rights and to establish the insured's liability, it is preferable for the injured party to name both the insurer and the insured as defendants, so that, after liability is established, compensation may be sought from the insurer. In this case, the insurer and the insured are jointly liable to the injured party, and the injured party may seek compensation from either; payment by either releases the other from liability to that extent (Babaei, 2010: 188).

4.14 Invalidity (Nullity) of the Insurance Contract

Nullity, in legal terminology, refers to the invalidity and lack of legal effects for actions or contracts that are concluded contrary to the law or later become invalid due to some defect. In regard to insurance contracts, observing the regulations and the validity of the contract is essential, as the absence of any substantive or formal requirement can result in the nullity or unenforceability of the policy (Yemeni, 2003). According to Article 9 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy and Article 34 of the Insurance Act, if the policyholder intentionally refrains from disclosing the truth or provides false statements, the insurance contract will be void and without effect, and the insurer may claim the remaining premium as well. According to Article 11 of the Insurance Act, if the policyholder insures property for more than its fair value with intent to defraud, the insurance contract will be void and the premium received shall not be refundable. If the insured item is also insured with another insurer for the same risk and period, with fraudulent intent, the insurance contract will be void (Article 22 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy). If it is discovered that the insured risk had occurred

before the conclusion of the contract, the policy will be void and without effect, and in case the premium has been received, the difference must be refunded (Article 18 of the Insurance Act). If the policyholder or their beneficiaries play a deliberate role in causing the damage, the contract will be void and no compensation will be payable. Changing the location or transferring ownership of the insured item without notifying and obtaining the consent of the insurer results in the invalidity of the contract. Failure to inform the insurer within the prescribed period—especially if it causes loss to the insurer—will result in the nullity or forfeiture of the right to compensation. If the policyholder prevents the insurer’s representatives from inspecting or from receiving the necessary documents and evidence, the insurer may refuse to pay compensation and consider the contract void.

4.15 The Principle of Subrogation

In fire insurance, which is a type of property insurance, after compensation is paid by the insurer, the rights of the policyholder to pursue and claim damages from the party responsible for the incident (the liable third party) are transferred to the insurer. This transfer of rights is known as the principle of subrogation and is one of the terms implied in the insurance contract (Article 30 of the Insurance Act; Article 29 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy, High Council of Insurance Directive No. 21). According to this principle, if a third party is responsible for the occurrence of the incident, the insurer, after compensating the policyholder, becomes subrogated to the policyholder’s rights to the extent of the amount paid and may seek recovery from the liable party. In this regard, the policyholder is obliged to refrain from any action that would compromise the insurer’s rights (such as settlement, waiver, or compromise with the liable party), as such actions are contrary to the insurer’s interests. According to Article 29 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy, persons such as partners,

employees, the spouse, and first-degree relatives of the policyholder are not considered third parties, except in cases of intentional damage. Furthermore, the insurer’s claim against the liable party is limited to the amount paid to the policyholder and cannot exceed that amount. Additionally, if the policyholder receives compensation directly from the liable party, there will no longer be any right to claim from the insurer, and vice versa. However, if only part of the damage is compensated, the policyholder may pursue the remainder from the liable party. Some legal scholars consider the application of the principle of subrogation to be limited solely to property insurance; however, this principle, subject to certain conditions, also applies to liability insurance arising from fire (Article 30 of the Insurance Act; Yemeni, 2003; General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy). Therefore, the principle of subrogation allows the insurer, after paying compensation to the policyholder, to seek recovery from the liable party (the responsible third party) for the amount paid. However, this right can be restricted or excluded in certain circumstances: the insurance contract may expressly provide that the insurer waives the right of subrogation. This possibility is often included to protect the interests of specific policyholders or by contractual agreement. For example, in a lease agreement, the landlord may include a non-recourse clause, thereby waiving the tenant’s liability for fire damage, and the insurer also waives recourse against the tenant (Mahdavi, 2019, p. 161). If the person responsible for the incident pays compensation directly to the policyholder, the insurer will have no right to bring a subrogation claim, as the loss has been compensated and the matter is resolved. If the policyholder settles or waives claims against the liable party (through compromise or waiver), according to Article 30 of the Insurance Act, the insurer’s right of subrogation will be extinguished, and the insurer will have no liability for compensation. The policyholder must not

undertake any action contrary to the insurer's rights. The insurer's right of recourse against the liable party as subrogee is subject to the statute of limitations applicable to the policyholder's original claim. If the policyholder's claim against the liable party is time-barred, the insurer's subrogation claim will also not be admissible (Abbaslou & Karami Ghehi, 2015, pp. 241–267). In cases where the liable party is a close relative of the policyholder (spouse, child, employees, partners, etc.), the default rule is that the insurer has no right of recourse except in cases of intentional damage (Naseri, 2007; Article 29 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy, Directive No. 21). Furthermore, the parties may agree in the insurance contract that the insurer shall not have the right to bring a subrogation claim. This condition is lawful and, with the parties' consent, may be included in the insurance policy (Babaei, 2010, p. 170).

4.16 The Policyholder's Right of Recourse Against the Liable Party

According to Article 30 of the Insurance Act of 1937, the insurer, to the extent that it pays compensation, is subrogated to the rights of the policyholder against those responsible for the incident. In other words, after compensation is paid by the insurer, the policyholder's right to claim damages from a third party (the liable party) is transferred to the insurer, and the policyholder no longer has any such right, except in specific cases. If the policyholder has insured their property for less than its actual value, the insurer is only liable for compensation in proportion to the insured amount relative to the real value. Therefore, if the loss incurred exceeds the amount paid by the insurer, the policyholder may claim the remaining loss from the liable party (Article 10 of the Insurance Act). In policies with a deductible (franchise)—meaning a part of the loss is borne by the policyholder—the policyholder retains the right to claim the amount of the deductible,

which was not paid by the insurer, directly from the liable party.

4.17 Involuntary Transfer of Rights and Obligations in Insurance Contracts

Upon the death of the policyholder, most of their financial rights and obligations are transferred to the heirs as successors, except for those rights that are inherently personal and non-transferable (Ahadi Parsa, 2018; Jalali et al., 2018). Involuntary transfer of contracts usually occurs in binding contracts, and the estate of the deceased is transferred involuntarily and by operation of law to the heirs. Regarding insurance, according to Article 17 of the Insurance Act of 1937, if the policyholder dies or the insured object is transferred to another person, provided that the heirs or the transferee fulfill all contractual obligations, the insurance contract remains valid and in their favor. However, both the insurer and the heirs or transferee have the right to terminate the contract. Furthermore, the insurer has the right, within three months from the date of the transferee's formal request for the transfer of the policy, to terminate the insurance contract. As a result, the death of the policyholder does not by itself terminate the insurance contract; rather, the rights and obligations arising from the insurance policy are transferred to the heirs and continue, unless one of the parties exercises their right to terminate the contract (Article 17 of the Insurance Act; Jalali et al., 2018).

4.18 Transfer of the Insured Subject

In an insurance contract, the property of the policyholder is under coverage. If the ownership of this property changes during the validity of the insurance policy, the continuation of the contract is subject to specific regulations. According to Article 17 of the Insurance Act of 1937, in the event of transfer of the insured subject to another person or the death of the policyholder, the insurance contract remains valid in favor of the transferee (the new owner), provided that

the transferee accepts the obligations of the previous policyholder. However, both the insurer and the transferee have the right to terminate the contract. The insurer may terminate the contract within three months after the transfer. Regarding the transferee, no specific period is determined, but they must act within a reasonable time, the determination of which, in case of dispute, is up to the court. Moreover, responsibility for overdue insurance installments up to the time of transfer remains with the previous owner (the transferor), and after the confirmation of the transfer, the transferee will be responsible for future obligations. If the transfer is made to several individuals, each transferee is jointly liable to the insurer for the entire obligations. In fire insurance, Article 20 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy of the High Council of Insurance (Regulation No. 21) stipulates that the transfer of rights and obligations arising from the policy is subject to the insurer's written consent.

5. Conclusion

The insurance contract is concluded by the offer of the policyholder and the acceptance of the insurer, and the policy is prepared as an official document reflecting the parties' intentions; its main purpose is to provide reassurance for the policyholder and to compensate possible damages by the insurer. Civil liability in liability insurance arising from fire is transferred to the insurer with the proper conclusion of the insurance contract. This contract, like other contracts, is subject to the general conditions of contract validity (Article 190 of the Civil Code), but special conditions such as the existence of insurable interest and specification of the insured risk are also necessary for its validity. In addition, certain formal requirements such as the inclusion of the date, names of the parties, subject and duration of insurance, amount of the premium, extent of the insurer's liability, and identification of the beneficiary must be stated in the policy. Although the civil liability of the insurer depends on the liability

of the policyholder, the policyholder's liability is realized only in relation to third-party claimants. In fire insurance, compensation relates to the policyholder's property and proving the existence of goods at the time of loss is necessary. Conversely, in liability insurance arising from fire, the insurer's obligation to compensate for losses to third parties is limited to the sum insured stated in the policy and the expert assessment. The role of the terms and conditions of the insurance contract is very important in the transfer and determination of the scope of the parties' liability. Terms such as premium payment and commencement of the policy's validity, observance of good faith by the policyholder, declaration of the insured location, notification of the incident within the prescribed period, and exclusion clauses—all are involved in the process of transferring liability (General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy of the High Council of Insurance, enacted 1987/11/18; Regulation No. 21). Ultimately, liability insurance arising from fire is arranged and enforceable based on the Insurance Act of 1937 and the Civil Liability Act of 1960, relying on the written proposal of the policyholder as an integral part of the policy. The special conditions of this policy are also determined in accordance with Article 13 of the General Conditions of the Fire Insurance Policy and in compliance with the regulations of the Civil Liability Act.

5.1 Suggestions

The role of insurance in the development and economic sustainability of modern societies—particularly in providing reassurance to economic and social actors—is undeniable. Benefiting from insurance services creates a safer and more risk-tolerant environment for individuals and companies, provided that the policyholder's legal and contractual obligations are properly fulfilled in accordance with the terms and conditions of the insurance contract. Therefore, full awareness and understanding by policyholders of their rights and obligations

is of great importance. Given the rapid growth of the insurance industry and the emergence of new branches such as engineering insurance, there is a clear need for further research in this area. The current information on various types of engineering insurance, their obligations, and the effects of related contracts is still insufficient.

References

- Al-Sheikh, M. (2002). The Legal Nature and Characteristics of the Insurance Contract. *Insurance Industry Quarterly*, 17(2), Serial No. 66.
- Ahadi Parsa, M. (2018). Subrogation in Contracts (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Safadasht Branch.
- Arzhang, A., Nazari, G., & Hosseini, S. A. (2014). A Critique on the Probability of Gharar in Insurance. *Islamic Jurisprudence and Principles*, 47(2).
- Esfandiari, E. (2016). Jurisprudential Foundations of Social Responsibility (Master's thesis). Payame Noor University, Tehran Province, South Tehran Center.
- Asadpour, E. (2016). Organizing the Impact of Contract Termination on the Acquired Rights of Third-Party Beneficiaries (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Qazvin Branch, Faculty of Management and Accounting.
- Ofoghi, R. (2013). Insurance Principles 4: Methods for Investigating Insurance Claims. Insurance Research Center, 1st Edition.
- Amini, M., & Khoroushi, A. (2008). The Scope of the Insurer's Obligation. *Insurance Industry Quarterly*, No. 85.
- Irani, A. (2019). Criminalization and Policy Response to Risky Behavior (Master's thesis). Shiraz University, Faculty of Law and Political Science.
- Babaei, I. (2010). Insurance Law. Organization for Research and Composition of University Humanities Books (SAMT), 9th Edition.
- Babaei, I. (2018). Civil Liability Law Based on Review and Critique of Judicial Opinions and Practices. Center for Publications of the Judiciary, Vol. 2, p. 298.
- Barikloo, A. (2013). Civil Liability. Mizan Publishing, 2nd Edition.
- Bigdeli, S. (2014). Comparative Study of "André Tunc's" Theory on the Basis of Civil and Contractual Liability and the Approach of Iran's Civil Law. *Islamic Law Research Journal*, 15(2), 133-160.
- Central Insurance of Iran. (2021). Court Decisions Section – Statute of Limitations. <https://www.centinsur.ir/fa-IR/Portal/5050/page/%D8%A2%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A1-%D9%85%D8%AD%D8%A7%DA%A9%D9%85>
- Parsa, A. A. (2019). Applied Science of Fire Insurance. Insurance Research Center, 3rd Edition.

Therefore, it is recommended that future studies focus particularly on specialized insurances such as engineering insurance, so that the legal and practical effects of these types of insurance, as well as the reciprocal responsibilities of the insurer and the insured, are thoroughly explained and documented.

- Parviziyounjali, N. (2018). Civil Liability of Pilgrimage Companies towards Iranian and Destination Country Pilgrims (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Garmsi Branch.
- Jamali Zadeh, A. (2008). Independent Insurance Contract. *Islamic Research Journal*, Faculty of Humanities, Shahid Bahonar University of Kerman, 2(3).
- Jahanshahi, G. (2013). Comparison of Financial Derivative Instruments with Insurance Contract (Master's thesis). University of Science and Culture, Tehran, Faculty of Humanities.
- Habibzadeh, M. (2017). Analysis of the Fundamental Unity of Contractual and Non-Contractual Liability. *Scientific Quarterly of Arav, Isfahan Judiciary*, 2(5), 219-240.
- Hozouri, M. (2021). Explanation of the Effects of Omission in Imamiyyah Jurisprudence and Its Adaptation to the Failure of Managers' and Government Employees' Legal Duties (Master's thesis). Imam Sadiq University, Faculty of Theology, Islamic Studies and Guidance.
- Khajeh Torab, F. (2018). Jurisprudential and Legal Study of Stipulations in Banking Transactions (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Shahrud Branch, Faculty of Humanities.
- Khorami, F. (1996). The Application of Insurance Principles in Credit Insurance. *Insurance Industry Quarterly*, No. 44.
- Khajeh Nouri, M. (1988). The Difference Between Cargo Insurance Policy and Liability Insurance Policy. *Transportation Industry Monthly*, No. 68.
- Khoroushi, A. (2011). Insurance Law. Tehran: Majd.
- Dashti Zangir, A. (2019). Theories of Fault and Risk in Iranian Law with a Comparative Study in Italian Law (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Garmsi Branch, Faculty of Law and Islamic Studies.
- Dashti Rahmatabadi, Z. (2014). Investigating the Expectation Gap between Insurer and Insured and Its Effect on Insured Satisfaction Using the Kano Model (Master's thesis). Yazd University, Faculty of Management and Accounting.
- Dehghani Tafti, M. (2020). Civil Liability of Sellers Lacking Legal Capacity in Electronic Sale (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Taft Branch, Faculty of Law.
- Rahimi, H., & Hajian, M. G. (2014). Economic Analysis of Elements of Civil Liability in Traffic Accidents. *Private Law Research Quarterly*, 2(7), 100-129.

- Rezaei, H. (2018). Liability of Guardians for Harmful Acts of Minors and Insane Persons in Iranian Law (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Shahrud Branch, Faculty of Humanities.
- Roozekafal, P. (2011). The Value of Insurance in Society. *Tazehaye Jahan Bimeh* (Insurance World News), No. 168.
- Zeynali, T. (2020). A Brief on Insurance Lawsuits in Court Practices. Cheragh Danesh Publishing, 1st Edition.
- Shokri, M. (2011). Civil Liability Resulting from Harmful Psychological Counseling (Master's thesis). Payame Noor University, Tehran Province, South Tehran Center.
- Salehi Zahabi, J. (2002). Governing Law on Civil Liability (Master's thesis). University of Tehran, Faculty of Law and Political Science.
- Ghaffari, H., & Zamani, M. (2017). Civil Liability Insurance for Mass Media. *Cultural and Communication Studies*, 14(50), 162-196.
- Abbaslou, B., & Karami Qaheyi, M. (2015). The Principle of Subrogation in Insurance Law. *Insurance Research Journal*, 30(1).
- Farjadi, M. (1997). Principles and Concepts of Commercial Insurance. Alborz Insurance Company.
- Farjadi, M. (1992). The Unconditional Right of the Insured to Terminate Property Insurance. *Central Insurance Quarterly*, No. 2.
- Ghanbari, T. (2015). The Effect of Intellectual Capital on Innovation in Iran Insurance Company in Tehran (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Tehran Central Branch, Faculty of Management.
- Karimi, A. (1999). Insurance Basics. 4th Edition. Central Insurance of Iran, Tehran.
- Karimi, A. (2010). Fire Insurance. 1st Edition. Jangal Publishing.
- Mazdarani, M. Y. (2017). Civil Liability Insurance Resulting from Nuclear Accidents (Master's thesis). University of Qom, University Campus.
- Montazeri, M. (2019). Application of Balanced Scorecard in Evaluating Asia Insurance Company Performance (Master's thesis). Raja Higher Education Institute, Faculty of Humanities.
- Mirzaei Abdali Yousofi, G. (2014). Obligations and Liabilities of Insurer and Insured in International Road Freight Transport Contracts in Iranian Law with Emphasis on CMR Convention (Master's thesis). Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht Branch, Faculty of Basic Sciences.
- Mahdavi, G., & Nasiri, F. (2019). Principles and Theoretical Foundations of Insurance, Vol. 1, 2nd Edition. Insurance Research Center.
- Nasiri, H. (2007). Liability of Insured and Insurer in Property Insurance. *Gavah Legal Quarterly*, Nos. 8 & 9.
- Vojdani, F. (1992). The History of the Emergence of Insurance, Its Importance, and Role in Trade. *Cooperation*, No. 17.
- Yomni, S. M. (2003). Expertise and Evaluation of Fire Insurance Issuance and Losses. Cultural Research Office, 1st Edition.
- Mary Kelly, Anne Kleffner, Martin Halek, & David Nickerson. (2017). The Role of Insurance in Reducing the Frequency and Severity of Fire Losses. University of the Fraser Valley.
- Rui-xia, Gao, H., & Wang, H. (2011). Discussion on the Fire Public Liability Insurance. *The 5th Conference on Performance-based Fire and Fire Protection Engineering*.
- Shanty Ika Yuniarti. (2021). Duty of Disclosure for Insurance Contracts: A Comparative Note of the United Kingdom and Indonesia. *Erasmus University Rotterdam, The Netherlands*, 1(1).